

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

Event calendar on training is online
Milestone M5.1
WP5 Training and capacity building

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Milestone M5.1

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ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results
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ESiWACE3 Milestone M5.1

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Type:

Dissemination level:

PU (for public use)

Delivery date:

Due date in month 3. Actual delivery date March 29th 2023.

Means of verifications:

Training calendar published online.

Achieved:

Yes

Comments:

The training calendar is currently realised as a continuation of the ESiWACE2 event calendar¹ as ESiWACE3 website is under development. A prototype version² of the new training calendar was developed and currently acts as a focal point for upcoming events. The new calendar will be published on the ESiWACE3 website.

¹ <https://www.esiwace.eu/events>

² <https://esiwace-training-calendar.notion.site/esiwace-training-calendar/7d09761c4d6b43698383df122b6754fe?v=75fb3ec811d542b993877daf7b6ba4be>

ESiWACE3 Milestone M5.1

Figure 1 ESiWACE3 training section

Event	Organizer	Registration deadline	Time	Format	Origin	Contents
Data assimilation	ECMWF	February 28, 2023	May 15, 2023 → May 19, 2023	In-person	https://events.ecmwf.int/event/333/	This five-day course focuses on describing
EUMETSAT/ECMWF NWP-SAF satellite data assimilation	ECMWF	February 28, 2023	May 22, 2023 → May 26, 2023	In-person	https://events.ecmwf.int/event/334/	This 5-day course is sponsored by EUME
High Performance Computing - Atos	ECMWF	February 28, 2023	May 2, 2023 → May 5, 2023	In-person	https://events.ecmwf.int/event/336/	The aim of this course is to introduce par
Summer School on Integrated Assessment Models	CMCC - Euro-Medi	March 1, 2023	July 3, 2023 → July 7, 2023	In-person	https://www.cmcc.it/training-programs/summer-school-on-integrated-assessment-models	Objectives The objective of the summer s
Use and interpretation of ECMWF products	ECMWF	March 27, 2023	October 9, 2023 → October 12, 2023	In-person	https://events.ecmwf.int/event/330/	The aim of the course is to increase partic
A hands-on introduction to Numerical Weather Prediction Models: Understanding and Experimenting	ECMWF	March 27, 2023	November 13, 2023 → November 17, 2023	In-person	https://events.ecmwf.int/event/331/	This five-day course is mainly practical ba
Parametrization of subgrid physical processes	ECMWF	March 27, 2023	November 20, 2023 → November 24, 2023	In-person	https://events.ecmwf.int/event/332/	This five-day course is a combination of k
Predictability and ensemble forecast systems	ECMWF	March 27, 2023	November 27, 2023 → December 1, 2023	In-person	https://events.ecmwf.int/event/335/	This five-day course will consider the chal

Figure 2 ESiWACE3 training calendar prototype